

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Comparison of algorithms for removing leakage in music learning scenario

Qingyuan Liu

Supervisor: Marius Miron

Co-Supervisor: Alia Morsi

August 31, 2023

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Abstract

The leakage of accompaniment in computer-aided music education scenarios is annoying, as it will prevent many Music Information Retrieval (MIR) algorithms from working properly. Although removing this leakage is favorable, few works directly address this issue. However, many algorithms have already been proposed in Source Separation or Acoustic Echo Cancellation (AEC) areas, and these two problems are similar to Leakage Removal. In this thesis, we compare the results of four different algorithms, two of them were originally designed for Source Separation or AEC problem and are modified for our problem. A dataset is constructed for this task and is publicly available. Results show that FullSubNet is generally advantageous compared to other models, but other models could be more favorable in specific cases.

Keywords: Source Separation, Acoustic Echo Cancellation, Leakage Removal, Artificial Neural Network

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Music Education is one of many applications of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) technology [1]. In a typical computer-aided music learning scenario, a software uses various MIR algorithms to retrieve useful information from users' performance, then evaluate users' performance and highlight the mistakes made by users accordingly. Playing accompaniment when practicing an instrument is desirable for learners. However, accompaniments played will leak into recorded user performance, and this leakage will prevent the following MIR algorithms from working properly. Therefore, removing this leakage is favorable in the described scenario.

1.2 Problem setup

As the first step, we only consider removing non-violin-family leakage against the violin performance. We assume that a beginner is practicing violin in a small-size room, and one device (mobile phone or laptop) is both playing accompaniment and recording user performance at the same time. The clean accompaniment audio played by the device is known and is referred to as "reference audio" in the following text. However, the acoustic characteristics of the room, microphone, and speaker are all unknown, and the user performance is also unknown. We also assume that the music piece to be performed is already known beforehand. Figure 1 depicts the typical scenario we interest in.

Figure 1: A typical scenario that accompaniment leaks into the record of user’s performance

1.3 Challenges

This exact setup poses many challenges to solving this problem. Those challenges prohibit us from using existing solutions directly. Following we list some of them.

- **The correlation between the leakage and user performance:** There is usually a strong correlation between the leakage and user performance, as they are parts of one ensemble. The strong correlation prevents us from using many source separation algorithms, as they require the sources to be uncorrelated with each other.
- **Low Signal-Noise Ratio:** As the sources of leakage are the speakers of the device being used, they are much closer to the microphone than the user. This causes the Signal-Noise Ratio (SNR) to be very low if the reference audio is audible to users.
- **Non-Linear Distortion:** To make the reference audio audible, we may need to play it at a very high volume. This could introduce non-linear distortion, especially for those low-end devices.
- **Beginners play poorly:** Usually, beginners’ performance contains many flaws, such as unstable tempo and pitch, heavily altered timber compared to masterpieces, etc. Usually, available datasets only contain decent performances from advanced players, so it is challenging to feed the models with data of poor performance.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Acoustic Echo Cancellation

The Acoustic Echo Cancellation (AEC) problem has undergone extensive research in recent decades because of its importance in telecommunication. The typical scenario of AEC problem can be described as follows:

$$y(t) = s(t) + e(t) = s(t) + h(r(t))$$

where $y(t)$ is the signal recorded by *near-end*, $s(t)$ is the target source we want to transfer to *far-end*, $e(t)$ is the echo signal, $r(t)$ is the reference signal and h is the environment transform applied to reference signal, which is usually assumed to be time-invariant. The goal of AEC problem is to find the best model f , which takes y and r as input, and generate an estimation \tilde{s} of s such that s and \tilde{s} are as close as possible. Note that it is easy to formulate our problem as a sub-category of AEC, given that their setups are similar.

Solutions to AEC problems typically fall into two different categories, neural-network-based on non-neural-network-based. Adaptive filters are a representative non-neural-network-based solution, which is attempting to model the environment with a series of filters [2]. Recently, neural networks have been proven to be useful in AEC problems. Zhang and Wang invented a Long-short Term Memory (LSTM) based network structure to address the AEC problem in 2018 [3]. The proposed model contains multiple stacked Bidirectional LSTM layers, and it uses the spectrogram as both input and output. It outperformed traditional Normalized Least Mean Square (NLMS) algorithms in various scenarios. Fazel et al. proposed a multi-task deep

recurrent neural network to solve AEC problem in 2019 [4]. Besides the estimation of near-end sources, the multi-task model proposed also yields an estimation of echo. This special design proved to be effective. In 2020, Zhang and Zhang proposed an AEC system that employs both adaptive filters and deep neural networks [5]. Experiments showed that this hybrid system gives better results and is more robust in unseen scenarios.

2.2 Source Separation

Audio source separation is a category of problems that try to split the audio of different sources from a mixed input. Our problem falls into this board category because we are trying to separate users' performance (target) audio and the echo audio. Similar to the case of AEC, solutions based on deep neural networks have become popular in recent years as they are more robust and yield better results than traditional signal processing algorithms.

The first work that applies neural networks to the source separation field was invented by Chandna et al, [6]. They use Short-Time Fourier Transformation (STFT) to convert the audio into a 2-dimensional spectrogram, then feed the spectrogram into a convolutional neural network that can split the sources. Contrary to the square-shaped convolutional kernels, which are widely used in the image processing field, they executed the convolution on two dimensions separately. This work also synthesizes the output waveform with the help of the phase of mixture input audio, and this approach is followed by many solutions that work on the frequency domain. In 2017, Jansson et al. proposed a deep U-Net model that addresses singing voice separation [7]. The deep U-Net model consists of multiple deep convolutional layers and skip connections are used to separate the singing voice from the mixture input, and that model gives state-of-the-art results at the moment of publication.

In 2018, Stoller et al. proposed a waveform-based U-Net model, named Wave-U-Net to handle source separation task [8]. Stoller et al. addressed many issues introduced by operating on the magnitude spectrum, including phase ignorance and fine-tuned hyperparameters of STFT. Wave-U-Net gives competitive results compared to its frequency domain counterparts and proves the possibility of manipulating waveform directly by deep neural networks.

Based on the aforementioned algorithms, many complex but efficient frameworks emerged and achieved many good results, such as Spleeter[9], Open-unmix[10] and Demucs[11, 12].

In 2021, Hao et al. proposed FullSubNet model as an effective framework, suitable for many source separation tasks [13]. As the name suggests, two submodels—full-band and sub-band—are used in the model, and both submodels contain two hidden LSTM layers. For each timestamp t , the f -th column of sub-band matrix S_f is obtained by the following way

$$S_f = [x_{f-N}, x_{f-N+1}, \dots, x_f, \dots, x_{f+N-1}, x_{f+N}]^T$$

in which N is a positive integer and x is the column of this timestamp in the input spectrogram. At each timestamp t , the spectrogram vector is first fed into the full-band submodel. The output is then concatenated with the calculated sub-band matrix and fed into the sub-band submodel and the output is taken as the result spectrogram. The network structure is shown in fig 2. Authors tested this framework on denoising, which is one type of source separation, and outperformed existing frameworks on this task.

2.3 Leakage Removal

In 2021, Wimmer et al. proposed a modified version of FullSubNet in order to solve the leakage removal problem in musical context [14]. Compared to the original version of FullSubNet, Wimmer et al. utilized the reference audio as an extra input. Mixture and reference audios are concatenated together and fed into the full-band submodel. Furthermore, they are both processed by the sub-band unit and again concatenated together with the output of the full-band submodel to be fed into the sub-band model to generate the final output. The network structure is shown in figure 3. The proposed model utilized the reference audio and outperformed the original FullSubNet by a significant margin.

2.4 Data Augmentation

Data Augmentation is known to be important to train a deep model properly because it can mitigate the overfitting problem and make the trained model more robust. Uhlich et al. first showed that data augmentation is helpful for source separation tasks as it will prevent overfitting and improve test performance [15]. Cohen-Hadria et al. conducted comprehensive research on the effect of data augmentation, based on U-Net and Wave-U-Net models [16]. They suggested three augmentations: Pitch shifting, time stretch and transform spectral envelope for singing voice only. They concluded that applying all three augmentations gives the best results for Wave-

Figure 2: Network Structure of FullSubNet. The second line in the rectangle describes the dimensions of the data at the current stage, e.g., “ $1(F)$ ” represents one F -dimensional vector, “ $F(2N + 1)$ ” represents F independent $(2N + 1)$ -dimensional vectors.

U-Net, and applying a single augmentation has little effect. However, for U-Net, essentially only pitch transformation works.

2.5 Dataset

2.5.1 Bach10

Bach10 dataset, created by Zhiyao Duan and Bryan Pardo, is a polyphonic music dataset [17]¹. It consists of the audio recordings of each part and the ensemble of ten

¹<https://labsites.rochester.edu/air/resource.html>

Figure 3: Structure of leakage removal version of FullSubNet. The second line in the rectangle describes the dimensions of the data at the current stage, e.g., “ $1(F)$ ” represents one F -dimensional vector, “ $F(2N+1)$ ” represents F independent $(2N+1)$ -dimensional vectors.

pieces of four-part J.S. Bach chorales, together with various symbolic data including MIDI scores. Four parts of each piece are performed by violin, clarinet, saxophone, and bassoon, respectively.

2.5.2 URMP

University of Rochester Multi-modal Music Performance (URMP) dataset comprises 44 multi-instrument musical pieces, which are assembled from coordinated but separately recorded performances of individual tracks [18]². Audios of individual tracks and musical scores in MIDI format are available for each piece. Videos of performance are also provided in the URMP dataset to support research about multi-

²<https://labsites.rochester.edu/air/projects/URMP.html>

modal approaches.

2.5.3 ACE Challenge

The Acoustic Characterisation of Environment (ACE) Challenge is hosted by the IEEE Audio and Acoustic Signal Processing Technical Committee [19]. The corpus used to construct the datasets used in the challenge is publicly available³, which contains Room Impulse Responses (RIRs) and noise profiles of many microphone configurations. We use these RIRs and noise profiles to augment our synthesized data.

2.5.4 Mango Future

Shenzhen Mango Future Tech. Co., Ltd.⁴ provided a set of 100 violin-piano ensemble scores, all in machine-readable format (MusicXML). Those scores are inputted manually by paid experts and have been reviewed multiple times to ensure correctness. Despite those scores not being publicly available because they are properties of Mango Future, the synthesized audio and MIDI tracks will still be available.

2.5.5 PHENICX-Anechoic

PHENICX-Anechoic dataset [20, 21]⁵ is created by the researchers of Universitat Pompeu Fabra and Aalto University. It consists of 4 passages of symphonic music. For each piece of symphony, individual anechoic recordings of each instrument are provided, and those individual recordings are aligned such that they can be mixed easily. However, the symbolic data of the PHENICX-Anechoic dataset merged all tracks from the same kind of instrument (for example, the MIDI information of all violin performance are merged into one single MIDI track), which makes it harder to utilize those symbolic data. As a result, the symbolic data in this dataset is not used to construct our dataset.

2.5.6 OpenSLR-RIR&Noises

Room Impulse Response and Noise Database (RIR&Noise)⁶, a part of Open Speech and Language Resources (OpenSLR), is originally proposed and used by Ko et al. in [22]. We use the noise part of the RIR&Noise database to augment our data.

³<http://www.ee.ic.ac.uk/naylor/ACEweb/index.html>

⁴<https://violy.app/en/>

⁵<https://www.upf.edu/web/mtg/phenicx-anechoic>

⁶<https://www.openslr.org/28/>

The noise part we use is originally constructed by Snyder et al. in the context of MUSAN corpus[23]. Those noises are selected from FreeSound platform⁷ and consist of various real-world foreground and background noises.

⁷<https://freesound.org/>

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Data Preparation

Figure 4: The flowchart of preparing training/validation data

Firstly, we select aligned violin/non-violin pairs from all four available datasets (Bach10, URMP, MangoFuture, PHENICX-Anechoic). We consider the violin parts as our target, and the non-violin parts as leakage to be removed. Note that one piece

Dataset	Symbolic Data			Recorded Audios		
	Piano	Flute	Clarinet	Piano	Flute	Clarinet
URMP		4	3		4	3
Bach10		10			10	
MangoFuture	100					
PHENICX-Anechoic					14	14
Total		117			45	

Table 1: Number of pairs selected from different datasets, according to instruments and availabilities of symbolic data and recorded audio

can generate more than one pair (If this piece contains more than one suitable non-violin instrument parts, and/or this piece contains more than one suitable violin parts.) As of now, the non-violin instruments considered are flute, clarinet, and piano. The number of pairs extracted from different datasets is presented in table 1. Note that to ensure the balance of the dataset, not all available parts from PHENICX-Anechoic are selected.

Secondly, we made a train-test split on the selected pair. We use the recorded audio as our test set, and symbolic data as our training and validating set. Randomly selected 10% of all synthesized data are used as the validation set. For the exact pipeline of data construction, readers can check the GitHub repository shown in section 5.3.

Thirdly, for each pair selected, if it consists of symbolic data, the audio will be synthesized by FluidSynth, and one SoundFont will be selected out of three SoundFonts gathered from the Internet. Then, both audios will be reverberated by applying a randomly selected room impulse response to them. After that, the target SNR value is randomly selected from -6, -3, 0, 3, and 6 dB, and both audios are mixed according to the selected SNR.

Fourthly, we mix a randomly selected noise into our audio. SNR is generated from a uniform distribution between -3 and 15 dB. The noise sample is randomly selected from RIR&Noise Database described in section 2.5.6.

Finally, for training and validation data, we chop the audios into 5-second long clips, with a 2.5-second hop length. For each clip, we use the final mixture as our mixed input, clean (not reverberated) leakage audio as our reference, and the reverberated violin audio as our target. The procedure of training and validation dataset is also shown in figure 4. The total length of synthesized audio exceeds 8 hours.

The test data is constructed using recorded audio in a similar way except we chop the audio into 30-second clips instead. However, when testing, multiple SNR setups are tested together, and as a result, the mixture is generated at the time of testing instead of doing so beforehand. Overall we have 32 test pairs using the given setup.

In order to facilitate the reproduction of our result and further improvement, the dataset used is available. Readers are referred to section 5.3 for more details.

3.2 Models

We selected 4 candidate models for our comparison: U-Net[7], Wave-U-Net[8], modified FullSubNet[14] and a RNN-based deep neural network, inspired by [3, 4]. The numbers of parameters of each model and training time consumption are shown in table ?? . all experiment is executed on a personal computer with Nvidia GTX 4060 video card and AMD Ryzen 7 5700G CPU. The details of the models' structure and training setup are listed below.

Model Name	U-Net	Wave-U-Net	RNN	FullSubNet
Parameter numbers	18.7M	18.9M	3.66M	6.20M
Training time	~7min	~90min	~15min	~160min

Table 2: Parameter numbers and training time of four candidate models

3.2.1 U-Net

Jansson et al. applied U-Net architecture to the task of singing voice separation in 2017 [7]. In our experiment, the exact structure of U-Net is similar to that of [7], except we have two separate encoders, one for the mixture input and the other for the reference audio. Specifically, each encoder has six layers, each layer consists of three parts: a 2D convolution of stride 2 and 5x5 kernel size, a batch normalization, and a leaky rectified linear units (ReLU) with $\alpha = 0.2$ as activation function. The sole decoder follows a symmetrical structure, it also has six layers, each layer consists of three parts: A deconvolution (a.k.a. transposed convolution) with stride 2 and 5x5 kernel, a batch normalization, a plain ReLU as activation function. The first three layers of the decoder have a 50% dropout, and the activation function of the last layer is sigmoid to generate a mask. Skip connections are added between encode and decode layers of the same resolution level. Note in our cases there are two skip connections connected to one decoder layer because we have two separate encode

subnetworks. The final prediction of magnitude is generated by multiplying the input magnitude with the mask (valued between 0 and 1). The network graph is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: The structure of U-Net

Regarding the training setup, to be consistent with the original work presented by Jansson et al., we replicate the setup they opted for in our experiment. When training, we use a 12-second segment instead of the usual 5-second segment. Audios are resampled to 8192 Hz, then we compute the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) with a Hann window of size 1024 and hop length 768. The aforementioned setup yields a 128-frame spectrogram, which is consistent with the original paper. The model is trained with the ADAM optimizer [24] with 0.001 learning rate, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, the loss function used is L_1 -norm (a.k.a. Mean Absolute Error). The batch size used is 16. The result waveform is reconstructed using the phase information of the mixture input. When testing, the input spectrogram is cut to 128-frame segments with 64-frame hop length. For each segment, we infer the result with the model, extract the central 64-frame as the final result, and discard both edges.

3.2.2 Wave-U-Net

Wave-U-Net was proposed by Stoller et al. in 2018 to solve the audio source separation problem [8]. In our experiment, we employ a modified Wave-U-Net to remove the leakage in the record. The Wave-U-Net we use consists of two downsampling subnets, one for each input waveform, and one upsampling subnet to reconstruct output prediction. A downsampling subnet consists of 12 downsampling layers, each downsampling layer contains a 1D convolution with kernel size 15, a leaky ReLU with $\alpha = 0.3$, and a decimation layer to halve the time resolution except in the last layer. For each layer, the number of filters increases by 24. The sole upsampling subnet consists of 12 upsampling layers, each upsampling layer contains a linear interpolation layer to restore time resolution, a 1D convolution with the exact same setup as in the downsampling subnet, and a leaky ReLU with $\alpha = 0.3$. The designated input size is 217075 samples (5 seconds), and the length of the output is 86201 samples in our setup, corresponding to the central part of the input. The network structure is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: The structure of Wave-U-Net

The Wave-U-Net model is trained with an Adam optimizer with learning rate of

10^{-4} , and the loss function used is Mean Squared Error. Due to the memory limit, we use 8 samples as a batch. To test the model, a window with length 217075 samples and hop length 86201 samples slides on the input waveform and generates the output directly.

3.2.3 FullSubNet

We reproduce a modified version of FullSubNet proposed by Wimmer et al. [14], the overall structure is shown in figure 3. To align with the original implementation, we first convert the input audios into 16 kHz sample rates, then generate magnitude spectrograms of both inputs by applying an STFT with the Hann window of 512-sample length and 256-sample hop length. Two spectrograms are first concatenated together through the frequency dimension and pass through the full-band subnet. The full-band subnet consists of two Long-short term memory (LSTM) layers with 512 units and a dense layer with 257 units and ReLU as the activation function. Furthermore, we can define the unfold operation on a spectrogram, which is used to generate the sub-band matrices. Unfolding a spectrogram $M \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$ will yield a 3D matrix $S \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F \times (2k+1)}$, in which T is the number of time frames, F is the number of frequency bins and k is a configurable parameter. The values of the entries of the sub-band matrix are defined as follows:

$$S_{t,f,i} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} M_{t,f+i-k}$$

Two input spectrograms are unfolded with $k = 15$, and two sub-band matrices are generated. Two sub-band matrices, together with the output of the full-band subnet, are concatenated together along the last axis as the input of the sub-band subnet. Sub-band subnet has a similar structure as the full-band subnet, it consists of two LSTM layers with 384 units and a fully connected layer to generate the complex Ideal Ratio Mask (cIRM) as prediction. The whole network has a 2-frame look ahead, which means a frame of output corresponds to two frames earlier in the input mixture.

The model is trained with Mean Squared Error loss function, ADAM optimizer with learning rate 10^4 . Due to the heavy memory requirement of this model, we use 2-sample batch when training. When testing, we cut the input spectrogram into small pieces, each piece has a small overlap with adjacent pieces to avoid artifacts on the edge of the output.

3.2.4 RNN

Figure 7: Network structure of original RNN

We propose a simple and computationally feasible recurrent neural network for comparison with other models. The exact network structure is shown in figure 7. First, the spectrograms of both mixed input and reference audios are calculated by applying a Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) with frame length 4096, hop length 1024, and the Hann window. Two spectrograms are concatenated together along the frequency axis as input to our network. The first layer is a 512-neuron fully connected layer with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) as the activation function. Following are two layers of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)[25] and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU)[26] is adopted as the recurrent unit. Both RNN layers have 256 units. Finally, another fully connected layer but with sigmoid as the activation function is employed to obtain the mask, and the output spectrogram is obtained by multiplying the mask with the spectrogram of mixed input.

The loss function selected is the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the ground truth and output spectrogram. Adam optimizer with learning rate 10^{-4} , $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$ is used as optimizer. Batch size used is 16. When testing, we obtain the output spectrogram and then use that spectrogram together with the phase info of

mixed input to reconstruct the audio through inverse STFT.

3.3 Evaluation

As mentioned in section 3.1, we have 32 tuples of convoluted audios and randomly selected noises for testing propose. When testing, we exhaustly enumerate possible values of truth vs. leakage Signal-Noise Ratio (SNR) $s_l \in \{-6, -3, 0, 3, 6\}$, and mixture vs. noise SNR $s_n \in \{18, 15, 12, 9, 6, 3, 0 - 3\}$. For each valid pair (s_l, s_n) , we first mix the audio of the violin and the audio of leakage together such that the resulting SNR is s_l dB, in which the leakage audio is considered as “noise”. Then we take the mixture and introduce noises, such that instrument sounds vs. noise SNR is s_n dB, in which the mixture of two instrument sounds is considered as our “signal”. After we generate the mixture, we try to remove the leakage and noise in the mixture by inferencing with four candidate models. The quality of output is evaluated with SI-SDR[27] metric. We also measure the end-to-end time requirement of every requirement (including inference, STFT ISTFT, etc.) because computational efficiency is crucial for real-time commercial applications.

Chapter 4

Results

The average SI-SDR of all test data of four candidate models is shown in table 3. For a given pair of (s_t, s_n) , the average result of each model is presented in the figures 8, 9, 10 and 11. We can observe that FullSubNet gives the best performance in terms of output quality, Wave-U-Net and RNN perform decently, and U-Net completely fails to generalize on test data. From the heatmap, we can see that the result will improve as the SNR goes higher, as we expected. Some example results are stored in the GitHub repository, readers can check 5.3 if interested.

The average time usage of processing one test input of each model is shown in table 4. Wave-U-Net and FullSubNet have significantly higher time usage likely because of their complex structure. However, the time usage of all four models is relatively short, and it is unlikely that the applications of these four models will be impeded due to the high time consumption.

Overall, FullSubNet gives the best output quality with a feasible computational resource requirement and thus is the strongest candidate among all four models. However, it is possible that other models can supervise in some scenarios. For example, if applications have high real-time requirements, or the computational resource is limited, one may opt to use other quicker yet effective models, such as our original RNN.

Model Name	U-Net	Wave-U-Net	RNN	FullSubNet
SI-SDR	-15.5	1.5	2.7	4.8

Table 3: Average SI-SDR of all test samples

Figure 8: The average SI-SDR of a given SNR setting of RNN model.

Model Name	U-Net	Wave-U-Net	RNN	FullSubNet
Avg. time usage(s)	0.15	1.05	0.30	0.73

Table 4: Average time consumption of processing a 30-second clip

Figure 9: The average SI-SDR of a given SNR setting of FullSubNet.

Figure 10: The average SI-SDR of a given SNR setting of U-Net.

Figure 11: The average SI-SDR of a given SNR setting of Wave-U-Net.

Chapter 5

Conclusion & Discussion

5.1 Conclusion

In this thesis, we investigate four candidate models to handle the leakage removal problem in the context of music education. We conclude that FullSubNet is generally the best choice among the four evaluated models, but other models could prevail in specific scenarios. We also aggregate a public-available dataset for this task, such that the following research can be executed on it.

5.2 Future Work

After analyzing the relatively small dataset, we have drawn some initial conclusions. However, having access to more data sources could be beneficial. It should be noted that the current data augmentation routine neglects common non-linear distortions that can occur in microphones and speakers when the sound intensity is close to the maximum limit of electronic devices. This type of distortion is frequently encountered in music education scenarios. Additionally, we did not take timber alteration into account, as beginners typically lack the necessary skills and tend to play the violin poorly.

The U-Net and Wave-U-Net models have a similar structure to their original counterparts but with the addition of an extra downconvolution subnetwork. However, the original structures were designed for different tasks and may not be the most optimal for our specific needs. By performing further fine-tuning on the U-Net and Wave-U-Net models, we could potentially improve their performance.

Currently, we solely rely on objective metrics for our evaluation process due to a lack of time to conduct subjective experiments. Despite the reliability of the SI-SDR metric in evaluating source separation algorithms, subjective evaluation remains crucial as it directly correlates with our perception of output quality.

5.3 Reproducibility

All source codes and datasets used in the experiment are available at https://github.com/seeker-Liu/master_thesis_leakage_removal_2023/. Note that anyone willing to run the codes needs to obtain the dataset according to the instructions in `README.md` because the size of the dataset exceeds the storage limit of GitHub.

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